

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 2E

Models, simulations, and related software (including pre and post processing and visualization codes)

System and Safety Analysis with SYSAI – A Statistical Learning Framework

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Background material: <https://tinyurl.com/wzzxbjkx>

System and Safety Analysis with SYS AI

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SYS AI (System analysis using Statistical AI) is a flexible statistical learning framework for safety analysis of complex aerospace systems with AI components, supports V&V and certification. Used for autonomous centerline tracking, DNN-based on-board collision avoidance, NN-adaptive control, acas-x, ttsafe, etc.

Analysis of training and testing data

High-dimensional safety envelopes

Operational safety envelopes

Robustness analysis under failures

DNN analysis

Data Management, Workflow, and Visualization Solutions at ORNL

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ENERGY

<https://tinyurl.com/2s3nh65s>

A Collection of Tools to Support Modern HPC

ADIOS: An adaptable and flexible I/O system for extremely fast file access, inter-job data transfers, and much, much more. Once data is described in ADIOS, it can be integrated into worldwide workflows.

MGARD: A technique for multilevel error-bounded lossy compression and refactoring of scientific data based on the theory of multigrid methods.

EFFIS

EFFIS: Workflow and code coupling framework that simplifies the integration of multiphysics codes with the supporting data capture, analysis, and storage.

VTK-m: A toolkit of scientific visualization algorithms for accelerated processor architectures for on-node data analysis. VTK-m is an enabling technology in ParaView, VisIt, Ascent, and other HPC data analysis tools.

Source code and examples at

<https://github.com/JHUAPL/Picante>

Picante

A Pure Java Implementation of NAIF/SPICE

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Poster available at <https://zenodo.org/records/8412282>

What is Picante?

- SPICE is a widely used software library for space missions developed by the Navigation and Ancillary Information Facility (NAIF) at NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory. It performs many common calculations such as
 - Spacecraft and celestial body ephemerides
 - Frame transforms
 - Instrument observation geometry
- Picante is a pure Java implementation of core SPICE routines, developed by the Analysis and Applications group of the Space Exploration Sector of the Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory. It has been used on several past and current NASA missions.
- Advantages over JNISpice:
 - It does not require the developer and user to install native SPICE libraries
 - It is thread safe (this is a limitation of NAIF/SPICE)
 - Available from Maven Central

EUROPA
CLIPPER

MESSENGER
MErcury Surface, Space ENvironment, GEochemistry, and Ranging

Aerie: Fostering an Open-Source Community for Mission Planning and Sequencing Software

What is Aerie?

Aerie is a fully open-source, permissively licensed (MIT) software system primarily sponsored by NASA's Advanced Multi-Mission Operations System (AMMOS) program to support spacecraft modeling and simulation, planning and scheduling, and sequencing/commanding operations on the ground.

Why Open Source?

- Instant access to latest deliveries, docs, and deployments
- Transparency of project planning and implementation (builds trust!)
- Enhanced collaboration and participation from customers, users or other interested parties (forms relationships!)

Unique Features

Open source, zero cost, and fully maintained

Mixed-initiative planning and scheduling

Modern UI and powerful API

Cloud native and scalable

Extensible modeling with low-code scheduling and constraint checking

Complete solution from plan creation through command generation

More Info

Project Landing Page
ammos.nasa.gov/aerie

Request a demo
eric.w.ferguson@jpl.nasa.gov

Get support on Slack
[NASA-AMMOS #aerie-users](#)

Fostering an Open-Source Community - Strategies

Transparency

Everything the team does and says is public!

- Public GitHub Issues
- Public GitHub Projects for sprint planning
- Design conversations are performed via GitHub discussions or on public Slack via huddles
- Public strategic roadmap (currently AirTable)
- Public governance and design meetings

Define Governance

Provide opportunity to give key stakeholders authority and ownership

- Project management committee (PMC) maintains roadmap and governance policies
- Liberal contribution model where people and/or organizations who do the most work will have the most influence on project direction
- Consensus-seeking decision making
- Contributors to SLIM, a community approach to developing a common set of best practices for NASA software

Reduce Barrier to Entry

Make everything as easy as possible for new users and contributors

- Easy < 5 min. install for rapid evaluation (working on no install required public instance)
- Thorough user-facing documentation including tutorials
- Public multi-mission extensions to kickstart mission-specific adaptations
- Well-documented APIs and migration guides
- Well-documented contribution guides, open CI/CD using GitHub Actions

Get Started

Active Outreach

Promotion is essential in the early days of a community - look the part

- Project landing page for potential and active community members
- Introductory video for website, conferences, and social media
- Actively engage every lead via demos and make sure to follow-up
- Respond rapidly to inquiries and questions to model a community of supportiveness
- Encourage all community members to participate in outreach

Challenges

Widespread mission adoption remains a challenge

- Organizations have different operations terminology and processes that must be mapped Aerie terminology - **use standards like CCSDS when possible**
- Organizations are often less invested in software they did not develop - **get other orgs involved early and often**
- Limited customer base seeking planning tools each year - **look outside NASA within defense and commercial sectors**

Understanding TPS fracture & failure

Augmented heating

Hayabusa-2 entry simulated

Further reading...

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LAVA ASPIRE FSI simulation

Simulation of Mars 2020 heatshield

Dragonfly Free-Flight simulation

Developing high-fidelity TPS models

Aeroshell radiative heating

Entry System Modeling Project Software Development For Enabling Entry, Descent, Landing Capabilities In Support of SMD missions - PI: A. Brandis & PM: J. Haskins

PuMA:
 Microscale modeling of material properties and performance

Icarus/Ares:
 3D simulation of recessing Arc Jet coupon

NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies

OpenME: Open source modifications to the NASA GISS ModelE GCM

PI: Gavin Schmidt

Developer(s): Maxwell Kelley, Igor Aleinov, and
Ken Mankoff (ken.mankoff@nasa.gov)

- ModelE is a global climate model (GCM)
- Code base is ~400,000 lines of FORTRAN
- First git commit 2000-07-11, but contains code from 1980s
- Historically significant - basis for James Hansen 1988 congressional testimony on climate change
- ModelE requires bit-for-bit reproducibility and traceability for all changes in model output.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11121979>

<https://www.giss.nasa.gov/tools/modelE/>

OpenME: Open source modifications to the NASA GISS ModelE GCM

- ModelE Includes ***Numerical Recipe*** algorithms, with a restrictive license: Cannot share code (Note: 100k+ copies of Numerical Recipe algorithms exist on GitHub)
- Some Numerical Recipe functions are now compiler-intrinsic. Remove the algorithm and it “just works”.
- Others require deep knowledge of numerical methods, stability, data types, etc.

Problem

- A) Development requires access to git history, which will always contain historical usage of Numerical Recipe algorithms
- B) Concerns around releasing 25+ years of bug-fixes and closed-source comments on politically charged topic
- => Development cannot be open
- Shallow git clones can be released. This is open source but not philosophically aligned with open source best practices